

An assessed framework for manufacturing sustainability based on Industry 4.0 under uncertainty

Khalid A. Eldrandaly¹, Mona Mohamed^{*2}, Nissreen El-Saber¹, and Mohamed Abdel-Basset¹

¹Faculty of Computers and Informatics, Zagazig University, Zagazig, 44519, Egypt

Emails: Khalideldrandaly@zu.edu.eg; naelsaber@fci.zu.edu.eg; mohamedbasset@ieec.org

²Higher Technological Institute, 10th of Ramadan City, Egypt

*Corresponding Author: Mona Mohamed (Email: mona.fouad@hti.edu.eg)

Abstract: Globalization and the rapid growth of technologies are the main challenges facing the manufacturer and its sustainability and survival. Sustainability for any manufacturing plays an important role in competitive advantage which make the manufacturing firm a sustainable competitor. Sustainability in manufacturing is integrated with Industry 4.0 (I4.0) to achieve benefits of economic, environmental, and social. But it has many criteria and factors and contains incomplete and uncertain information. So, we used the neutrosophic sets to overcome this incomplete information and treat with uncertainty environment. The Single-Valued Neutrosophic Set (SVNS) is used to evaluate these criteria, which include three values (Truth, indeterminacy, and falsity). The SVNS is integrated with Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) methods. The MCDM concept is used in this paper to deal with many conflicting criteria. A Decision-making trial and evaluation laboratory (DEMATEL) is utilized for determining the relation between five main criteria and fourteen sub-criteria in this study. Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is used to compute the weights of the main and sub-criteria. Our framework is applied to a real case study in Egypt to show the validity of our framework.

Keywords: Sustainability; Industry 4.0; AHP; Single-Valued Neutrosophic Sets; SVNSs; Multi-Criteria Decision Making; MCDM; DEMATEL.

1. Introduction

In the previous centuries, the industrial revolutions continued until advent of the fourth industrial revolution, known as I 4.0. This revolution includes the use of many technologies that help automate and digitalize operations. The manufacturing industry has undergone many radical changes [1].

This new digital industrial transformation has had a positive impact on manufacturing organizations. This made manufacturing more intelligent which led to businesses changing their way of working. I4.0 is an umbrella for various technologies such as big data analytics (BDA), Internet of Things (IoT) and cloud computing, Cyber-Physical systems (CPS), information and communications technology (ICT), Enterprise Architecture (EA), Enterprise Integration (EI) and Blockchain (BC) [2].

The benefits of utilization of I4.0 technologies in manufacturing are (i) it helped in the emergence of so-called smart manufacturing. Smart manufacturing is expressed in [3] as “manufacturing machines are characterized with interconnection through wireless networks according to modern manufacturing paradigm, monitored by sensors, and controlled by advanced computational intelligence to enhance the quality of product, increase productivity, and sustainability with reducing costs.” (ii) manufacturing system becomes an integrated and cooperative production system that responds to any changing requirements and conditions in real-time [4]. (iii) high level of digitization

through exchanging data, communication among parts, products, machines, and human-machine interaction (HMI). (iv) Optimization through energy and resource consumption. (v) Global competitiveness through productivity and operational efficiency. (vi) Beneficial decisions through tracking products effectively and analyzing the market on an ongoing basis. (vii) The cost is reduced, and profits are increasing by processing effective information are improving the production planning decisions [5, 6, 7]. (viii) Improvement of product development by transforming the traditional production and operations management techniques [6].

Consequently, manufacturing firms are becoming sustainable by applying I4.0 technologies. Despite it being a complicated process, not simple. From the TBL perspective [8] one of the sustainability requirements for the firm is achieving a balance between the economic, environmental, and social pillars. Sustainability of manufacturing according to TBL represents: Environmentally, products are environment-friendly through using resources efficiently. Socially, the production process is based on ethics and sustainability. Economically, manufacturing processes are highly efficient in saving energy, natural resources utilization and achieving a better global market reputation [9].

The sustainability of manufacturing based on I4.0 has many various conflict criteria, so the Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) is used to overcome this problem. Numerous MCDM techniques offer a huge variety of approaches for solving complex decision-making problems such as TOPSIS, DEMATEL, Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)...etc. MCDM is used in assessments containing numerous criteria to support decision-makers (DMs) and experts to make decisions based on their preferences by breaking the problems into smaller portions [13]. These techniques have been increasingly used in manufacturing practices [14]. According to [15] MCDM deal with many types of problems that contain huge and conflict criteria.

Researchers in [16] have introduced techniques to strengthen MCDM through utilizing Fuzzy Set (FS) where its function is to assign a degree of membership ranging between [0-1] for each element. In [17] an improvement of FS, called Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets (IFS) is introduced. It considers the membership degree, non-membership degree, and hesitation degree. But the FS can't deal efficiently with the incomplete data due to lack of the indeterminacy value concept.

Neutrosophic theory embraces the idea of FS and IFS more comprehensively. It assigns a degree of membership, indeterminacy, and non-membership function for each element [18]. Furthermore, [19,20] proposed many benefits of neutrosophic theory such as: (i) Neutrosophy helps experts to present their opinions about uncertain preferences by using the degree of indeterminacy to present obscure information. (ii) It deals with different conditions of decision-making through applying truthiness, indeterminacy, and falsity. (iii) It expresses odds between DMs and experts. (iv) It can handle uncertainty and various environments.

All of these are strong motivations for consolidating neutrosophic theory with MCDM techniques to rank and select the best solution (alternative) among possible solutions (alternatives) based on calculation weights of criteria through an expert panel [15]. For the maximum benefit, the criteria with the maximum weight is selected.

The focus of modern organizations is not limited to profitability, but it spans to eco-friendly items production, time utilization of challenging tasks, and increased productivity. In short, modern organizations seek sustainability [21].

The research on sustainability of manufacturing based I4.0 is in its early stages of growth [22]. In Section 2 of this work, more details are given via the Web of Science (WoS) database.

In this study, we will adopt the idea of the influence of I4.0 on manufacturing firms to be environmentally, socially, and economically sustainable. This study aims to fulfill the following objectives:

1. Attempting to answer the question (using literature analysis): Can the adoption of I4.0 technologies have a positive impact on promoting sustainability in manufacturing?

2. Identifying I4.0 enablers or criteria and sub-criteria that affect the achievement of manufacturing sustainability using literature.
3. Assessing the impact of determined I4.0 main and sub-criteria on each other to achieve sustainable manufacturing through a questionnaire offered to a committee of decision makers (DM) and experts.
4. Determine degree of influence among main and sub-criteria using the hybrid framework of MCDM with neutrosophic theory (N-DEMATEL).
5. Applying AHP-based neutrosophic for recommending the most positive influential criteria on three pillars of Triple Bottom Line (TBL).
6. Applying the proposed framework on a case study of real manufacturing firms.

This paper is organized as follows: section 2 presents systematic analysis of related articles and the research methodology used in this study, section 3 presents the literature review of I4.0 and sustainability of manufacturing related I4.0 illustrating basic concepts and technologies. Section 4 clarifies the proposed developed framework for criteria interrelations. In section 5, the hybrid framework validation is assessed through real case study. Finally, conclusions are highlighted in section 6.

2. Systematic Analysis and Research Methodology

In this section, systematic analysis is performed on the available published documents on the study topic. The analysis process facilitates knowing current trends of research in the literature related to a specific field [23,24]. Therefore, research papers and articles on “sustainable manufacturing” and “sustainable manufacturing based I4.0” are analyzed. The source of articles is Web of Science (WoS) database from 2015 until 2020. WoS database contains numerous famous publications and articles in different domains. Figure 1 illustrates the steps to be followed in the methodology.

The proposed research methodology consists of four steps as shown in Figure 1 and summarized below:

Step1: Search WoS database: The database is searched using two key concepts; “sustainable manufacturing” and “sustainable manufacturing based I4.0”.

Step2: Trend Analysis: Based on the research results, the study focuses on number of publications in the field per year, type of the publication and area of research. These data are summarized and interpreted allowing for further insights. Table 1 shows the summarized search results.

Step3: Trend Analysis Results (potentials): the trend results are categorized into two parts. First part is for extracting the gaps and limitations in the research area. This is followed by highlighting the potential motivations for contributions in the manufacturing sustainability using I4.0 as part two.

Step4: Influence Evaluation Model: a model is developed for assessing the influence of criteria from I4.0 on the manufacturing sustainability.

Fig 1. Steps of research methodology.

Table 1. Summary of previous work in sustainability manufacturing and I4.0.

	Sustainability of manufacturing	Sustainability of manufacturing based I4.0
No. of Publications	5446	231
Category of publications	Article:	3746
	Proceeding papers:	1260
	Review:	453
	Early Access:	149
	Book chapter:	135
	Editorial chapter:	35
	Books	2
Areas and fields	ENGINEERING:	2741
	Business Economics:	1562
	Computer Science:	301
	Telecommunications:	53
	Chemistry:	229

3. Literature Concepts

3.1 Industry 4.0

In 2011, I4.0 was presented at the Hannover Fair [24]. Later, in 2013, the German government introduced I4.0 [25]. The term “I4.0” is associated with other terms such as smart manufacturing, smart production, or smart factories, due to the use of numerous technologies [26]. For [27], I4.0 includes the connection between physical and digital technologies such as CPS, cloud computing, big data...etc to share information and make intelligent decisions to gain the organization a competitive advantage in the market through fulfilling the needs of clients.

Technologies of I4.0 in [28] are classified into two categories front-end technologies and base technologies as shown in Fig. 2. Other researchers support a different view of base technologies as [29] supposes CPS, IoT, cloud, fog computing, and BDA are yield to base technologies. Reseach in [30] assumes CPS, IoT, ICT, EA, and enterprise integration are base technologies. Moreover, technologies of I4.0 as IoT, CPS, and artificial intelligence (AI) in [33] is a futuristic construct that boosts the development of production systems. That is due, as mentioned in [34] to the capacity of its technologies to enhance the energy, equipment, and use of the human resource. Thus, Organizations are becoming more sustainable and competitive globally.

The goal of I4.0 is to connect intelligent products, manufacturing processes, and machines by developing a network between them [31]. Conforming to that, [32] proposes that organizations are improving their capabilities for data processing through I4.0 which permits each part to interact with each other. Achieving organizational sustainability requires a balance between three pillars of Triple Bottom Line (TBL) economic, environmental, and social perspectives as [35] reported sustainability for industries in Brazil-based three pillars.

Fig. 2. Classification of I4.0 Technologies adapted from [28]

3.2 Sustainability of Manufacturing Based Industry 4.0

Sustainable Manufacturing is defined in [36] as processes and systems that are merged to use resources such as energy and raw materials wisely for producing a product of high quality, customer satisfaction, and regulatory compliance. Although manufacturing organizations strive to balance three pillars to achieve sustainability, there may be challenges that are threatening their sustainability. The plastics industry in [5] suffers from challenges of three pillars. Addressing such industrial challenges through [37,38] by adopting I4.0 technologies that utilize energy efficiently and effectively and tracking the life cycle of the product from design to delivery. In [39] there are many countries are adopting I4.0 technologies in their manufacturing sector like Australia, China, and Thailand for instance. General Electric Company (GE) is adapted the Predix platform which helps in connectivity, analytics, and machine learning, processing, and analysis big data for adding multiple benefits to its users[40].

CPS [41] is used in many sectors such as automotive, medical, and manufacturing aerospace with a special focus in the United States and the European Research Council. This is due to its ability to acquire and collect data through the sensor and to deal with a large volume of data. This technology is named 5C as for its five levels: Smart Connection, Data-to-Information Conversion, Cyber, Cognition, and Configuration. It consolidates information and machines to enhance the performance of the industry and the decision becomes decentralized [42]. Optimization of production through dynamic models is used in CPS to manage and organize the activities through manufacturing procedures [43]. Its ability to collect and analyze data according to [44] makes it able to increase productivity with higher quality and low cost, promote growth, and increase the efficiency of workers.

IoT supports the manufacturing process and offers advanced methods such as monitoring, managing, and optimizing the operation of manufacturing. International Telecommunication Union (ITU) defined IoT as the ability to connect anytime, anyplace to anyone [45,46]. Also, plays an important role in the observation of energy consumption to save energy thus the energy crisis is reduced [47].

Big Data Analytics are used to obtain information and make an accurate decisions based on analyzing the collected data obtained via IoT technology [9]. The utilization of big data Positively affected the quality of production and monitoring of the damage and work of each machine to facilitate the maintenance of machines and equipment [48].

The manufacturing process can be environmentally friendly by integrating Additive manufacturing to reduce scrap production and facilitates complex designs so, the product becomes flexible and consistent [49]. Applying these new technologies aims to increase efficiency and improve the performance of the entire industrial chain. I4.0 technologies have a socially robust impact from the perspective of [44] in transforming operating patterns, design, product services, and production systems to smarter patterns and dispensing with human beings. [50] believes that technologies have a positive impact on the environment through energy consumption is more efficient and safer. Based on [51] I4.0 technologies are adapting to achieve circular economies. The conclusion from the foregoing is that the I4.0 technologies are promoting sustainable development by positively affecting

TBL. Many quantitative and qualitative studies are aimed to analyze and evaluate the impact of the I4.0 on the sustainability of each pillar of TBL's pillars. Robust Best Worst Method (RBWM) is one of the MCDM techniques used to assess the degree of influence of enablers in [10] for I4.0 technologies on the sustainability of manufacturing. Developed frameworks are used Fuzzy Evaluation Method (FEM) for identifying the importance of enablers of I 4.0 as in [52].

Factors affecting sustainability are classified and categorized in [53] into cause and effect. It used DEMATEL as requirements of government (F1), Social responsibility (F2), Green image (F3), and other factors. Grey-based DEMATEL is used in [54] to evaluate the influential strength of drivers for I4.0 to achieve sustainability in Supply Chains (SC). AHP is the most famous technique of MCDM which is used to analyze the drivers in [55] for advanced sustainable manufacturing. A hybrid MCDM techniques-based fuzzy decision-making trial and evaluation laboratory and analytic network process (FDANP with PROMETHEE) in [56] to analyze sustainable risks in the manufacturing of surgical cotton for helping manufacturing organizations avoid unwanted accidents, as well as through early knowledge for sustainable risks.

In this section, the following literature concepts are introduced; Industry 4.0, sustainability of manufacturing based I4.0, and related technologies. The proposed framework is introduced in the following section.

4. Mathematical Model

As mentioned in introduction section, we are identifying I4.0 criteria and subcriteria that achieve sustainability of manufacturing. Assessment process for I4.0's criteria/subcriteria is vital process.

4.1 DMs perspectives based MCDM with neutrosophic uncertainty method

In this section, we integrated the SVNSs with the MCDM methods to evaluate the criteria I4.0 with sustainability manufacturing. Firstly, the DEMATEL method is applied to show the interrelationships among criteria. The SVNSs are used to scale as [57]. Secondly, the SVNSs AHP is used to compute the weights of the criteria. Fig 3 shows the proposed framework of this paper.

4.2 Determine influencing main/sub criteria Based on N-DEMATEL

Step 1: Select decision-makers and experts who have expertise in this field. The main and sub-criteria of sustainability manufacture based on I4,0 technologies are collected. Then decision-makers offered to evaluate the criteria based on the Single-Valued Neutrosophic Numbers (SVNNs) as in [57].

Step 2: Constructed Pairwise comparison matrices based on relation between criteria by DMs panel.

Step 3: Transformation of pairwise comparison matrices for criteria to deneutrosophic form via Eq. (1).

$$s(a_{ij}) = \frac{(2+T-I-F)}{3} \quad (1)$$

Where T, I, F represent truth, indeterminacy, and falsity, a_i refers to the value in the comparison matrix and i refers to the number of criteria.

Fig. 3. The proposed Framework

Step 4: Apply the aggregation method to aggregate the opinions of experts into one matrix to obtain the direct relation matrix.

Step 5: Normalize the direct relation matrix as Eqs. (2, 3)

$$S = K * Y \tag{2}$$

where Y refers to the direct relation matrix as in the previous step.

$$K = \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq i \leq n} (\sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij})} \quad (i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n) \tag{3}$$

Where a_{ij} represent the sum of each raw (i) in matrix Y , $\max_{1 \leq i \leq n} (\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij})$ represent the maximum value of a_{ij} and n refers to the number of criteria. a_{ij} refers to the value in the direct relation matrix.

Step 6: Production of total relation matrix

We use the MATLAB software to obtain the total relation matrix as Eq. (4)

$$T = S(I - S)^{-1} \tag{4}$$

Where I refers to the identity matrix.

Step 7: Get (R) and (C) for total relation matrix T.

The Sum of rows (R) and columns (C) are obtained as in Eqs. (5,6).

$$T = [a_{ij}]_{n \times n}, i, j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$$

$$R = \left[\sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij} \right]_{1 \times n} = [a_j]_{n \times 1} \tag{5}$$

$$C = \left[\sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij} \right]_{1 \times n} = [a_j]_{n \times 1} \tag{6}$$

Step 8: Construct a causal and effect diagram by the horizontal axis R+C and vertical axis R-C. the values of R-C determine cause and effect criteria/subcriteria. criteria/sub criteria are cause when its values of R-C are positive.

4.3 Neutrosophic AHP Method

Step 1: Repeat steps from 1 to 4 mentioned in section 4.1 to obtain the aggregated pairwise comparison matrix.

Step 2: Normalize aggregated/Average comparison matrix as Eq. (7).

$$\text{Norm}_{ij} = \frac{a_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n (a_j)}, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \tag{7}$$

Where $\sum_{j=1}^n (a_j)$ the sum of criteria per column in the aggregate matrix, a_j point to the preference of criterion in aggregated comparison matrix.

Step 3: Compute the weights of criteria by the row average of the previous step.

Step 4: Check the consistency ratio (CR) as [58].

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} \tag{8}$$

$$\text{Where, } CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} \tag{9}$$

Where n point to number of criteria/sub criteria in this study, RI is consistency ratio where its value determines based on number of criteria/sub criteria are used in the model.

5. Case Study and Results

We apply our methodology in a manufacturing enterprise in Egypt. This enterprise is responsible for producing household electrical appliances such as irons, food blenders, ceiling fans, vacuum cleaners, etc. The criteria of sustainable manufacturing based on I4.0 are introduced to the enterprise to increase the performance and achieve sustainability..

5.1 Results of Neutrosophic DEMATEL

Step 1: Table 2. represents demographic information about the experts who evaluated the criteria in this study. We collected five main criteria and fourteen sub-criteria as in Table 3.

Step 2: Four comparison matrices are obtained.

Step 3: Transform these matrices into crisp values-based Eq. (1).

Step 4: Obtain the direct relation matrix by the aggregation method.

Step 5: Obtain the normalized relation matrix based on Eq. (2,3) as Table 4.

Step 6: Obtain the total relation matrix as in Table 5.

Step 7: Obtain the values of R-C and R+C

Step 8: Obtain the causal diagram for the main and sub-criteria. Fig 4. shows the causal diagram. From Fig 4. C_5 is the best criteria and C_1 is the worst criteria.

Table 2. Demographic information about the expert panel

Demographic Information	Gender	Age	Qualifications	Job Title
First member	Male	40	Ph.D.	Executive Manager
Second member	female	35	Bachelor	Financial Consultant
Third member	Male	45	Master	Maintenance Engineer
Fourth member	Male	40	Bachelor	Quality and Safety Manager

Table 3. The main and sub-criteria

Main Criteria	Sub-Criteria
DBA(C1)	Exploration of new customers and opportunities (C1-1). Technologies Upgradation for analyzing(C1-2)
Additive Manufacturing(C2)	Green design and environmentally friendly process (C2-1). Ease testing and prototyping (C2-2) Health and safety (C2-3) Reduction cost of operations (C2-4)
IoT(C3)	Real time control (C3-1) Efficiency monitoring and traceability(C3-2)
Flexible Manufacturing (C4)	Reduction lead time (C4-1) Increase productivity and quality(C4-2) Energy efficient consumption (C4-3) Enhance ethical and sustainable process (C4-4)
CPS(C5)	Interactions between human and machine are friendly (C5-1) Automation DM instead human (C5-2)

Table 4. Normalized relation matrix

Criteria	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5
C_1	0.051368	0.067292	0.067806	0.073456	0.067806
C_2	0.238221	0.051368	0.076538	0.049313	0.0488
C_3	0.170256	0.225449	0.051368	0.084244	0.043663
C_4	0.147062	0.462174	0.125288	0.051368	0.078593
C_5	0.190045	0.305762	0.31727	0.135555	0.051368

Table 5. Total relation matrix

Criteria	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5
C_1	0.18232	0.223463	0.15843	0.13358	0.114364
C_2	0.378852	0.218592	0.177966	0.123952	0.108227
C_3	0.368491	0.427165	0.176694	0.171914	0.116716
C_4	0.461954	0.741624	0.310335	0.182239	0.183401
C_5	0.548225	0.686383	0.526992	0.293146	0.177187

Fig. 4. Causal and effect for main criteria

For sub-criteria, we applied the Neutrosophic DEMATEL method in five sub-criteria. From Fig 5,6,7,8 and 9, we found that C₁₋₁ has the highest impact and C₁₋₂ has the lowest impact. C₂₋₄ has the highest impact and C₂₋₁ has the lowest impact. C₃₋₂ has the highest impact and C₃₋₁ has the lowest impact. C₄₋₄ has the highest impact and C₄₋₁ has the lowest impact. C₅₋₂ has the highest impact and C₅₋₁ has the lowest impact.

Fig. 5. Causal and effect for BDA sub- criteria

Fig. 6. Causal and effect for Additive Manufacturing sub- criteria

Fig. 7. Causal and effect for IoT sub- criteria

Fig. 8. Causal and effect for Flexible Manufacturing sub- criteria

Fig. 9. Causal and effect for CPS sub- criteria

5.2 Results of Neutrosophic AHP Method

Start with the aggregated comparison matrix, then normalized it using Eq. (7) in Table 6. After that, from Table 6. we compute the weights of criteria by the row average in the normalized comparison matrix. The weights of the main criteria are obtained as $W_1 = 0.13026, W_2 = 0.151669, W_3 = 0.172228, W_4 = 0.239525, W_5 = 0.306318$. This means that C_5 has the highest weight and C_2 has the lowest weight. Then we compute the weights of sub-criteria and compute the global weights by multiplying the weights of main criteria by the weights of local criteria. Fig 10. shows the weights of global criteria. From Fig. 10. we deduce that C_{5-2} has the highest weight and C_{2-1} has the lowest weight.

Fig 10. The global weights

Table 6. Normalized aggregated comparison matrix by the AHP method

Criteria	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5
C_1	0.064456	0.060512	0.106234	0.186468	0.233628
C_2	0.298915	0.046192	0.119915	0.125181	0.168142
C_3	0.213634	0.202734	0.08048	0.213851	0.150442
C_4	0.18453	0.415607	0.196293	0.130397	0.270796
C_5	0.238465	0.274955	0.497077	0.344103	0.176991

6. Conclusions

Merging I4.0 in the industrial sector contributes to making flexible and efficient processes to produce better quality products with low cost to achieve competitive advantage. I4.0 has a significant impact on digitalizing manufacturing-based technologies as seen earlier.

This study contributes to the understanding of how manufacturing achieves sustainability according to TBL through I4.0 technologies. So, manufacturing firms are encouraged to fully integrate new technologies which have a positive impact on TBL pillars into their practices.

Wherefore, we developed a hybrid framework based on MCDM techniques to analyze and evaluate the factors and criteria based on sustainability manufacture related to I4.0. Four decision-makers and experts are selected to evaluate these criteria. Five main and fourteen sub-criteria are collected. The framework has been applied to a real case study in a manufacturing firm in the electrical industry. SVNSSs are integrated with the DEMATEL and AHP methods in this work. The DEMATEL method is used to show the relation between the main and sub-criteria while the AHP method is used to compute the weights of the criteria.

Many methods like TOPSIS, VIKOR, and Entropy, can be applied to this problem in future directions. Moreover, the proposed framework can eventually be applied to many MCDM problems with more criteria.

References

1. Popkova, Elena G., Yulia V. Ragulina, and Aleksei V. Bogoviz. "Fundamental differences of transition to industry 4.0 from previous industrial revolutions." In *Industry 4.0: Industrial Revolution of the 21st Century*, pp. 21-29. Springer, Cham, 2019.
2. Ghobakhloo, Morteza, and Ng Tan Ching. "Adoption of digital technologies of smart manufacturing in SMEs." *Journal of Industrial Information Integration* 16 (2019): 100107.
3. Wang, Jinjiang, Yulin Ma, Laibin Zhang, Robert X. Gao, and Dazhong Wu. "Deep learning for smart manufacturing: Methods and applications." *Journal of Manufacturing Systems* 48 (2018): 144-156.
4. Thompson, K. D. "Smart manufacturing operations planning and control program." Gaithersburg, MD: National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) (2014).
5. Lu, Yang. "Industry 4.0: A survey on technologies, applications and open research issues." *Journal of industrial information integration* 6 (2017): 1-10.

6. Stentoft, Jan, Kent Wickstrøm Jensen, Kristian Philipsen, and Anders Haug. "Drivers and barriers for Industry 4.0 readiness and practice: a SME perspective with empirical evidence." In Proceedings of the 52nd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences. 2019.
7. Nguyen, Truong, Z. H. O. U. Li, Virginia Spiegler, Petros Ieromonachou, and Yong Lin. "Big data analytics in supply chain management: A state-of-the-art literature review." *Computers & Operations Research* 98 (2018): 254-264.
8. Nara, Elpidio Oscar Benitez, Matheus Becker da Costa, Ismael Cristofer Baierle, Jones Luis Schaefer, Guilherme Brittes Benitez, Leonardo Moraes Aguiar Lima do Santos, and Lisianne Brittes Benitez. "Expected impact of industry 4.0 technologies on sustainable development: A study in the context of Brazil's plastic industry." *Sustainable Production and Consumption* 25 (2021): 102-122.
9. Kumar, Ravinder, Rajesh Kr Singh, and Yogesh Kr Dwivedi. "Application of industry 4.0 technologies in SMEs for ethical and sustainable operations: Analysis of challenges." *Journal of cleaner production* 275 (2020): 124063.
10. Yadav, Gunjan, Anil Kumar, Sunil Luthra, Jose Arturo Garza-Reyes, Vikas Kumar, and Luciano Batista. "A framework to achieve sustainability in manufacturing organisations of developing economies using industry 4.0 technologies' enablers." *Computers in Industry* 122 (2020): 103280.
11. Abdel-Basset, Mohamed, Abdualлах Gamal, Ripon K. Chakraborty, and Michael J. Ryan. "Evaluation of sustainable hydrogen production options using an advanced hybrid MCDM approach: A case study." *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* (2020).
12. Nabeeh, Nada A. "A Hybrid Neutrosophic Approach of DEMATEL with AR-DEA in Technology Selection." *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* 31, no. 1 (2020).
13. Mardani, Abbas, Edmundas Kazimieras Zavadskas, Zainab Khalifah, Norhayati Zakuan, Ahmad Jusoh, Khalil Md Nor, and Masoumeh Khoshnoudi. "A review of multi-criteria decision-making applications to solve energy management problems: Two decades from 1995 to 2015." *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 71 (2017): 216-256.
14. Ren, Yaping, Chaoyong Zhang, Fu Zhao, Matthew J. Triebe, and Leilei Meng. "An MCDM-based multiobjective general variable neighborhood search approach for disassembly line balancing problem." *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems* (2018).
15. Liu, Jian, Peng Liu, Si-Feng Liu, Xian-Zhong Zhou, and Tao Zhang. "A study of decision process in MCDM problems with large number of criteria." *International Transactions in Operational Research* 22, no. 2 (2015): 237-264.
16. Zadeh, Lotfi A. "Fuzzy sets." In *Fuzzy sets, fuzzy logic, and fuzzy systems: selected papers by Lotfi A Zadeh*, pp. 394-432. 1996.

17. Atanassov KT. Intuitionistic fuzzy sets BT - intuitionistic fuzzy sets: theory and applications. In: Atanassov KT, editor; 1999. p. 1e137. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-7908-1870-3_1. Heidelberg: Physica-Verlag HD.
18. Smarandache F. Neutrosophy: neutrosophic probability, set, and logic: analytic synthesis & synthetic analysis. American Research Press; 1998.
19. Abdel-Basset, Mohamed, Gunasekaran Manogaran, and Mai Mohamed. "Internet of Things (IoT) and its impact on supply chain: A framework for building smart, secure and efficient systems." *Future Generation Computer Systems* 86 (2018): 614-628.
20. Nabeeh, Nada A., Mohamed Abdel-Basset, and Gawaher Soliman. "A model for evaluating green credit rating and its impact on sustainability performance." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 280 (2021): 124299.
21. Wang, Miaomiao, Rui Zhang, and Xiaoxi Zhu. "A bi-level programming approach to the decision problems in a vendor-buyer eco-friendly supply chain." *Computers & Industrial Engineering* 105 (2017): 299-312.
22. Manavalan, E., and K. Jayakrishna. "A review of Internet of Things (IoT) embedded sustainable supply chain for industry 4.0 requirements." *Computers & Industrial Engineering* 127 (2019): 925-953.
23. J. Webster, R.T. Watson, "Analyzing the past to prepare for the future: writing a literature review," *MIS Q.* 26 (2) (2002) xiii–xxiii.
24. Echchakoui, Saïd, and Nouredine Barka. "Industry 4.0 and its impact in plastics industry: A literature review." *Journal of Industrial Information Integration* (2020): 100172.
25. L. Xu, E. Xu, L. Li, "Industry 4.0: state of the art and future trends," *Int. J. Prod. Res.* 56 (8),(2018) 2941–2962.
26. Li, Ying, Jing Dai, and Li Cui. "The impact of digital technologies on economic and environmental performance in the context of industry 4.0: A moderated mediation model." *International Journal of Production Economics* (2020): 107777.
27. A. Haleem, M. Javaid, "Additive manufacturing applications in industry 4.0: A review," *J. Indus. Integ. Manage.* 4 (4) (2019) 1930001.
28. Reinhardt, Ingrid Carla, Jorge C. Oliveira, and Denis T. Ring. "Current perspectives on the development of Industry 4.0 in the pharmaceutical sector." *Journal of Industrial Information Integration* 18 (2020): 100131.
29. G. Aceto, V. Persico, A. Pescape, "Industry 4.0 and health: internet of things, big data, and cloud computing for healthcare 4.0," *J. Indus. Inform. Integ.* (2020) In press, journal pre-proof Available online 13 February Article 100129.
30. M. Yli-Ojanperä, S. Sierla, N. Papakonstantinou, V. Vyatkin, adapting an agile manufacturing concept to the reference architecture model industry 4.0: a survey and case study, *J. Indus. Inform. Integr.* 15 (2019) 147–160.

31. Luthra, Sunil, Anil Kumar, Edmundas Kazimieras Zavadskas, Sachin Kumar Mangla, and Jose Arturo Garza-Reyes. "Industry 4.0 as an enabler of sustainability diffusion in supply chain: an analysis of influential strength of drivers in an emerging economy." *International Journal of Production Research* 58, no. 5 (2020): 1505-1521.
32. Ivanov, Dmitry, Alexandre Dolgui, and Boris Sokolov. "The impact of digital technology and Industry 4.0 on the ripple effect and supply chain risk analytics." *International Journal of Production Research* 57, no. 3 (2019): 829-846.
33. Pacaux-Lemoine, Marie-Pierre, and Damien Trentesaux. "Ethical risks of human-machine symbiosis in industry 4.0: insights from the human-machine cooperation approach." *IFAC-PapersOnLine* 52.19 (2019): 19-24.
34. Lasi, Heiner, Peter Fettke, Hans-Georg Kemper, Thomas Feld, and Michael Hoffmann. "Industry 4.0." *Business & information systems engineering* 6, no. 4 (2014): 239-242.
35. Nara, Elpidio Oscar Benitez, Caroline Gelain, Jorge André Ribas Moraes, Lisianne Brittes Benitez, Jones Luís Schaefer, and Ismael Cristofer Baierle. "Analysis of the sustainability reports from multinationals tobacco companies in southern Brazil." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 232 (2019): 1093-1102.
36. Machado, Carla Gonçalves, Mats Peter Winroth, and Elias Hans Dener Ribeiro da Silva. "Sustainable manufacturing in Industry 4.0: an emerging research agenda." *International Journal of Production Research* 58, no. 5 (2020): 1462-1484.
37. Frank, Alejandro Germán, Lucas Santos Dalenogare, and Néstor Fabián Ayala. "Industry 4.0 technologies: Implementation patterns in manufacturing companies." *International Journal of Production Economics* 210 (2019): 15-26.
38. Cezarino, Luciana Oranges, Lara Bartocci Liboni, Nelson Oliveira Stefanelli, Bruno Garcia Oliveira, and Lucas Conde Stocco. "Diving into emerging economies bottleneck: Industry 4.0 and implications for circular economy." *Management Decision* (2019).
39. Orzes, Guido, Robert Poklemba, and Walter T. Towner. "Implementing industry 4.0 in SMEs: a focus group study on organizational requirements." In *Industry 4.0 for SMEs*, pp. 251-277. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham, 2020.
40. GE Predix platform: the foundation for digital industrial applications. <https://www.ge.com/digital/predix-platform-foundation-digital-industrial-applications>, (accessed 25 Jan. 2018).
41. Bagheri, Behrad, Shanhu Yang, Hung-An Kao, and Jay Lee. "Cyber-physical systems architecture for self-aware machines in industry 4.0 environment." *IFAC-PapersOnLine* 48, no. 3 (2015): 1622-1627.
42. Ivanov, Dmitry, Boris Sokolov, and Marina Ivanova. "Schedule coordination in cyber-physical supply networks Industry 4.0." *IFAC-PapersOnLine* 49, no. 12 (2016): 839-844.

43. Ivanov, Dmitry, Alexandre Dolgui, Boris Sokolov, Frank Werner, and Marina Ivanova. "A dynamic model and an algorithm for short-term supply chain scheduling in the smart factory industry 4.0." *International Journal of Production Research* 54, no. 2 (2016): 386-402.
44. Rießmann, Michael, Markus Lorenz, Philipp Gerbert, Manuela Waldner, Jan Justus, Pascal Engel, and Michael Harnisch. "Industry 4.0: The future of productivity and growth in manufacturing industries." *Boston Consulting Group* 9, no. 1 (2015): 54-89.
45. F. Tao, Y. Cheng, L. Da Xu, L. Zhang, B.H. Li, CCIoT-CMfg: cloud computing and internet of things-based cloud manufacturing service system, *IEEE Trans. Ind. Informat.* 10 (2) (2014) 1435–1442.
46. L. Atzori, A. Iera, G. Morabito, The internet of things: a survey, *Comput. Netw.* 54 (15) (2010) 2787–2805, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2010.05.010>.
47. Bagdadee, Amam Hossain, Li Zhang, and Md Saddam Hossain Remus. "A Brief Review of the IoT-Based Energy Management System in the Smart Industry." In *Artificial Intelligence and Evolutionary Computations in Engineering Systems*, pp. 443-459. Springer, Singapore, 2020.
48. Bal, Hasan Çebi, and Çisil Erkan. "Industry 4.0 and competitiveness." *Procedia Computer Science* 158 (2019): 625-631.
49. Bhatia, Manjot Singh, Suresh Kumar Jakhar, Sachin Kumar Mangla, and Kishore Kumar Gangwani. "Critical factors to environment management in a closed loop supply chain." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 255 (2020): 120239.
50. Dalenogare, Lucas Santos, Guilherme Brittes Benitez, Néstor Fabián Ayala, and Alejandro Germán Frank. "The expected contribution of Industry 4.0 technologies for industrial performance." *International Journal of Production Economics* 204 (2018): 383-394.
51. Ghobakhloo, Morteza. "The future of manufacturing industry: a strategic roadmap toward Industry 4.0." *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management* (2018).
52. Shayganmehr, Masoud, Anil Kumar, Jose Arturo Garza-Reyes, and Md Abdul Moktadir. "Industry 4.0 enablers for a cleaner production and circular economy within the context of business ethics: a study in a developing country." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 281 (2020): 125280.
53. Agarwal, Sucheta, Vivek Agrawal, and Jitendra Kumar Dixit. "Green manufacturing: A MCDM approach." *Materials Today: Proceedings* 26 (2020): 2869-2874.
54. Luthra, Sunil, Anil Kumar, Edmundas Kazimieras Zavadskas, Sachin Kumar Mangla, and Jose Arturo Garza-Reyes. "Industry 4.0 as an enabler of sustainability diffusion in supply chain: an analysis of influential strength of drivers in an emerging economy." *International Journal of Production Research* 58, no. 5 (2020): 1505-1521.

55. Shankar, K. Madan, P. Udhaya Kumar, and Devika Kannan. "Analyzing the drivers of advanced sustainable manufacturing system using AHP approach." *Sustainability* 8, no. 8 (2016): 824.
56. Bhalaji, R. K. A., S. Bathrinath, S. G. Ponnambalam, and S. Saravanasankar. "A soft computing methodology to analyze sustainable risks in surgical cotton manufacturing companies." *Sādhanā* 45, no. 1 (2020): 1-22.
57. Abdel-Basset, Mohamed, Abduallah Gamal, Nour Moustafa, Ahmed Abdel-Monem, and Nissreen El-Saber. "A Security-by-Design Decision-Making Model for Risk Management in Autonomous Vehicles." *IEEE Access* 9 (2021): 107657-107679.
58. Nabeeh, Nada A., Mohamed Abdel-Basset, Haitham A. El-Ghareeb, and Ahmed Aboelfetouh. "Neutrosophic multi-criteria decision-making approach for iot-based enterprises." *IEEE Access* 7 (2019): 59559-59574.
59. Jawahir, I. S., and O. W. Dillon Jr. "Sustainable manufacturing processes: new challenges for developing predictive models and optimization techniques." In *Proceedings of the first international conference on sustainable manufacturing, Montreal, Canada*, pp. 1-19.

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